

FUNGAL INFECTION OF THE NAILS DUE TO PROBABLE HANDLING OF WET CURRENCY NOTES

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ABSTRACT

Onychomycosis is a fungal infection of the nail beds and it is caused by dermatophytes, yeast or nondermatophytes. More and more, Onychomycosis is viewed as being more than a cosmetic problem. Onychomycosis in immunocompromised clients can pose a more serious health problem. Dermatophytes are the most frequently implicated causative agents. Despite improved personal hygiene and living environment, onychomycosis continues to spread and persist. This case report is that of a young Nigerian male who probably got infected by prolonged unprotected handling of wet, soggy currency notes in his place of work.

KEYWORDS: Dermatophytes, onychomycosis, wet currency notes, protection.

INTRODUCTION

Fungal infection is a relatively common disease worldwide. Such fungal or mycotic infection could involve the nails, hair and skin. Different fungal species are known to infect different parts of the body and many non-fungal disorders may clinically simulate a mycotic infection. This makes it necessary for proper diagnosis with basic laboratory testing such as a potassium hydroxide preparation (KOH prep) and fungal culture.

Incidentally, our index case probably contracted the infection from prolonged contact with possibly infected wet currency notes. Unfortunately, we were unable to test any of the suspected currency notes for fungal elements neither do we see other colleagues of our client under study with similar problems. We did not do fungal culture because we do not have the facility for that.

Case Report

A young male Nigerian was seen at a private clinic in Warri, Delta State, complaining of prolonged deformation of all of his fingernails and some of his toenails. He said that the problem began some months ago after he was involved in sorting out old and wet currency notes in his workplace.

He works in one of the new generation banks in the country. He reported that soon after the completion of the work, which took about three weeks and which was done without wearing hand gloves, that he noticed some rashes on two of his fingers of the left hand.

This was followed by a gradual involvement of other fingernails until all the ten fingernails were involved.

Initially, what he had was a darkening around the proximal part of the nail bed but gradually over time, the entire fingernails got darkened. They eventually got heaped up and thickened, breaking easily and then became deformed.

Apparently, after one month, he noticed the same process as above on the toenails. This started on the two big toes and eventually spread to the other toenails.

It was at this point that he presented at the hospital for treatment.

Examination revealed darkened, heaped-up fingernails but normal fingers and toes. There were no signs of bacteria infection noted. The toes also revealed similar findings as above but only on four toes.

A working diagnosis of onychomycosis was made probably due to prolonged handling of infected currency notes. Retroviral test after counseling was negative and full blood count was normal and random blood sugar was normal.

The problem was explained to him and treatment modality was explained to him. He was subsequently put on an oral anti-fungal medication and was to be reviewed monthly during drug refilling.

Unfortunately, he defaulted from treatment because he felt that there was no noticeable change in the texture of the fingernails after one month of treatment. He then went for traditional treatment, and applied some native herbal concoctions on the nails which led to burns and infection in the nail beds with formation of frank pus under all the fingernails.

He then reappeared at the clinic and was advised one more time on the need for compliance to drug management. Antibiotics were prescribed for him and follow-up visit showed marked improvement while adequate anti-fungal therapy was re-introduced.

DISCUSSION

Fungal infection of the nail bed, nail plate or both, otherwise known as tinea unguium or onychomycosis is mostly caused by trichophyton infection of one or more, but rarely all fingernails or toenails. The species most commonly found is *Trichophyton rubrum*. Saprophytic fungi may rarely cause (<5%) of onychomycosis (Berger, T. G. 1998).

Onychomycosis is a fungal infection of nails caused by dermatophytes, yeast or non-dermatophytes molds and represents about 30% of mycotic cutaneous infections. In spite of improved personal hygiene and living environment, onychomycosis continues to spread and persists. Dermatophytes are the most frequently implicated causative agents in onychomycosis (Kaur, R. *et al* 2007).

The prevalence rate of onychomycosis is determined by age, predisposing factors, social class, occupation, climate, living environment and frequency of travel. The prevalence is higher (25%) in patients with immunodeficiency viral infection (Kaur, R. *et al* 2007).

Studies have shown that prevalence of onychomycosis increases with age, reason for which may include poor peripheral circulation, diabetes, repeated nail trauma, and longer exposure to pathogenic fungi (Aditya, G. K, 1997).

Studies of patients with either psoriasis or diabetes indicate that both types of patients have a much higher chance of contracting onychomycosis than normal persons. If a diabetic is a male, older and has either peripheral vascular diseases or has a family history of onychomycosis his chances of contracting the condition at some point are increased (Aditya, G. K, 1997).

In patient with psoriasis who presents with a nail abnormality, it may be difficult to decide whether this is due to psoriasis, onychomycosis, a combination of the two or another cause (Aditya, G. K, 1997).

Also, because of the high prevalence of onychomycosis in diabetics, the availability of oral antifungal agents that treats effectively may play a role in optimal long-term management of diabetes and diseases related to it.

About 10% of the population has onychomycosis. Risk factors include tinea pedis, pre-existing nail diseases, older age, male sex and circulatory diseases.

Toenails are ten times more commonly infected than fingernails. About 60 – 80% of cases are caused by dermatophytes (*Trichophyton rubrum*). Many of the remaining cases are caused by non-dermatophyte molds such as *Aspergillus*, *Scopulariopsis* and *Fasarium*. Immuno-compromised patients may have *candidial* onychomycosis (Beers, M. H 2006)

Onychomycosis secondary to non-dermatophytes moulds is seen most frequently in the elderly, in patients with skin diseases that affect the nail and in immuno-compromised patients (Kaur, R. *et al* 2007).

There are usually no symptoms the affected nails are often brittle and friable, breaking easily. They are lusterless and hypertrophic.

Onychomycosis is difficult to treat because of the long duration of therapy required and the frequency of recurrences.

Griseofulvin was the first orally effective anti-fungal agent and the only one available for over twenty years. Although it helped many patients with dermatophytic skin infection, it was ineffective against infection caused by candida, as well as systemic and subcutaneous fungal infection (Zeid S. A 1994).

The continued search for an anti-fungal drug with a broad spectrum of activity led to the introduction of new antimycotic drugs, which have opened a new era in the treatment of fungal infections (Elewski, B. 1997). They are safer and the risk for toxicity is rare.

Physicians and patient now benefit from significant advances in the treatment of superficial fungal infection of the skin, hair, nails and mucosa.

Despite these advances, treatment failure still occurs for a variety of reasons, many of which can be preventable. Whenever available, physicians are encouraged to use recommended regimens that have been substantiated as being optimal. Under-dosage or improper treatment duration commonly leads to treatment failure due to sub-therapeutic tissue concentration (Rosso Del et al 1998).

Overall, approximately 20 – 30% of onychomycosis patients exhibit only partial clearance or fail treatment with any of the newer oral agent. Occasionally, patient may present with combination of onychomycosis and “onychobacteriosis” just like our client did after the application of herbal concoction on the nail beds. This too, could affect the management especially if not properly diagnosed and treated appropriately.

Our index case got infected while sorting out possibly infected bank notes. He was involved in the job without wearing protective hand gloves nor even face mask and this probably explains why his fingernails were infected first and then more severely than his toenails. Such protective devices such as wearing hand gloves would have prevented the prolonged contact between the possibly infected currency notes and the patients; and wearing face masks would have removed the risk of inhaling fungal spores in the environment. Also, the vault should have ventilators that helps clear the environment of air-borne droplets of fungal spores.

This case report is to highlight the possibility of our currency notes been able to transmit fungal infection and then to serve as a call for proper handling of the currency notes. Proper handling of currency notes must be encouraged and these includes the stoppage of the act of spraying notes during parties and the celebrants dancing on the sprayed notes; not squeezing the notes; not the writing on the currency notes and not washing the notes in our laundry. It is recommended that the currency notes be handled gently and arranged stretched out in our dry wallets.

We also recommend that central laboratories with facilities to do fungal cultures be established in the national geographical regions.

REFERENCES

Aditya. G. K. 1997: Psoriatic and diabetic patients have high risks for onychomycosis. *Mycol Observ*, 6 (5): 6

Beers, M. H., and Porter, R. S. (Eds). 2006: The Merck Manual of Diagnosis and Therapy, 18th edition. Nail Disorder. In: Dermatologic Disorders. Merck Research Laboratories USA. pg 932 – 1027.

Berger, T. G. Skin and Appendages 1998: In: Current Medical Diagnosis and Treatment. 37th edition. Tierney, L. M., McPhee, S. J., and Papadakis, M. A. (Eds). Appleton and Lange, USA. pp. 111 – 179.

Elewski, B. 1997: Newer anti-fungals are treatment choice against onychomycosis. *Mycol Observ* 6, No. (5): 2.

Kaur, R., Kashyap, B., and Bhalla, P. 2007: Onychomycosis – Epidemiology, diagnosis and management. *Nig. Biomed Sci J*. 4 (2) 7 – 15.

Rosso Del, J. Q., and Gupta, A. K. 1998: Optimising Treatment with Oral Anti-fungal Agents. Based on lecture presentation at the 56th Annual American Academy of Dermatology Meeting, Orlando, USA.

Zeid, S. A., and Halim, S. 1994: Short term Oral Lamisil (terbinafine) in the treatment of moccasin tinea pedis. *African Clinician* 18. Medicine Group (Journal) Ltd.

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